

Research Article

Analysis and Design of Steel Braced Framed with Different Bracing location by Using Etabs

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ABSTRACT

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Introduction: Steel structures are widely adopted in high-rise construction because of their high strength, flexibility, and ease of fabrication. However, they are highly susceptible to lateral forces generated by wind and earthquakes, which may lead to excessive sway and instability. To enhance lateral stiffness and stability, bracing systems are introduced in steel frames. Bracings act as diagonal members that transfer lateral loads through axial action, thereby reducing bending moments and inter-storey drift. The present study will focus on the seismic analysis and design of a G+30 steel framed building incorporating bracing configurations such as X types, using ETABS software. Different plan geometries Square, L, C, and T-shaped buildings will be modeled to evaluate the influence of structural shape on performance. Bracings will be placed at different locations, including corners, building faces, and core, to assess their effect on the structural response. The analysis will be carried out using the Response Spectrum Method as per IS 1893 (Part 1):2016, and design will be performed according to IS 800:2007. Parameters such as storey drift, displacement, and base shear will be evaluated and compared for each configuration.

Keywords: -. RCC Structure, Steel Bracing System, ETABS, Seismic Analysis, Response Spectrum, IS 1893:2016, IS 800:2007.

INTRODUCTION

In modern construction, steel structures have gained wide popularity due to their high strength, durability, and ability to resist heavy loads with minimal self-weight. They are extensively used in high-rise buildings, industrial sheds, bridges, towers, and warehouses where both strength and flexibility are essential. However, the stability of steel frames under lateral loads such as wind and earthquakes remains one of the most critical aspects of structural design.

Unlike vertical loads, which act downward and are resisted primarily by gravity, lateral loads create horizontal forces that can cause swaying, torsion, and even collapse if not adequately resisted. In a steel frame, these lateral forces tend to deform the structure sideways, generating bending in beams and columns. Excessive lateral deflection can lead to non-structural damage, instability, and discomfort to occupants.

To overcome these problems, engineers use bracing systems, which are structural members arranged in specific patterns within the steel frame to provide lateral stability. Bracing forms a triangular configuration that resists horizontal movement through truss action, thereby enhancing the overall stiffness and strength of the structure. [19]

Role of Bracing in Steel Structures

Bracing systems act as an effective lateral load-resisting system in steel buildings. They connect the beams and columns to form a stable framework that transfers horizontal forces safely to the foundation. The function of a bracing system is not only to resist wind or earthquake loads but also to minimize bending moments and shear forces in vertical and horizontal members.

The main roles of bracing can be summarized as follows:

1. Increases Lateral Stiffness:

By introducing diagonal members, bracing reduces the degree of lateral sway and increases the rigidity of the structure.

2. Improves Strength and Stability:

Braced frames can carry higher loads without undergoing excessive deformation, maintaining the overall stability of the building.

3. Reduces Member Forces:

Since part of the lateral load is resisted by the braces in axial tension and compression, the bending moments in columns and beams are reduced significantly.

4. Enhances Ductility:

Properly designed bracing systems allow controlled energy dissipation during dynamic events like earthquakes, improving the structure's ability to withstand cyclic loads.

5. Economical Solution:

Compared to rigid moment-resisting frames, braced frames require smaller sections for columns and beams, making them a cost-effective option.

Need For the Study

Rapid urbanization and increasing demand for high-rise buildings have led to the extensive use of steel structures due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, faster construction, and flexibility in architectural planning. However, these structures are highly susceptible to lateral forces generated by earthquakes and wind loads, which can adversely affect their stability and safety. Therefore, it is essential to enhance their lateral load-resisting capacity through suitable structural systems.

Steel bracing is one of the most effective and economical methods for improving the seismic performance of buildings. The efficiency of a bracing system depends not only on its type but also on its location within the structure and the overall building configuration. Buildings with irregular plans such as L, C, and T shapes often exhibit complex behavior under seismic loading due to uneven distribution of mass and stiffness.

Although several studies have been carried out on braced steel frames, limited information is available regarding the comparative performance of different plan shapes with bracing provided at various locations such as corners, faces, and core regions. Understanding the influence of these parameters is important for selecting an efficient structural arrangement that minimizes displacement and improves overall stability.

Therefore, this study is undertaken to evaluate the seismic behavior of steel braced frame structures with different plan configurations and bracing locations using ETABS. The findings of the study will help structural engineers identify suitable bracing arrangements for achieving safer, more stable, and economical steel buildings in earthquake-prone regions.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

T. Y. Yang et al. (2020) studied the seismic performance of eccentrically braced steel frames designed using conventional and equivalent energy design procedures. The study concluded that the equivalent energy design approach improved seismic resilience and reduced repair costs while maintaining adequate structural safety.

A. Acosta et al. (2024) evaluated steel buildings with different eccentrically braced frame configurations. The results showed that seismic response is highly influenced by structural configuration, and lower-storey drifts were more critical under earthquake loading.

C. Zhang et al. (2023) investigated steel braced frames equipped with self-centering buckling restrained braces. The proposed system effectively reduced lateral displacement and enhanced seismic performance, especially under strong earthquake motions.

A. Kianmehr et al. (2021) examined the influence of different bracing systems on the collapse probability of steel structures. The study found that bracing type, ductility, and building height significantly affect seismic safety and collapse resistance.

M. Jalalvandi et al. (2022) compared steel frames incorporating Shape Memory Alloy (SMA) and Buckling Restrained Braces (BRB). The results indicated that both systems effectively reduced inter-storey drift, while SMA braces provided superior control of residual displacement.

A. Osman et al. (2023) studied the use of steel X-bracing with shear links for seismic strengthening. The findings demonstrated that the retrofitting system significantly improved structural stiffness, strength, and displacement control under earthquake loading.

Noor Mohammed (2016) carried out a nonlinear pushover analysis of RCC buildings with base isolation systems. The study showed that pushover analysis effectively predicts structural performance and helps assess seismic safety at different performance levels.

Yousuf Dinar (2014) presented a descriptive study on pushover analysis of RCC structures. The research concluded that nonlinear pushover analysis provides reliable evaluation of seismic performance through parameters such as base shear, displacement, and storey drift.

A. Kadid (2008) performed pushover analysis on reinforced concrete frame structures subjected to seismic loading. The study concluded that properly designed frame structures can achieve satisfactory seismic performance and damage control during earthquakes.

Shubham P. Dhoke (2017) compared different lateral load-resisting systems for multi-storey buildings using ETABS. The results indicated that the selection of an appropriate lateral load-resisting system significantly influences storey displacement, drift, and overall seismic behavior.

Summary and Gap Identification

The literature review indicates that steel bracing systems significantly improve the seismic performance of structures by increasing stiffness, reducing lateral displacement, and enhancing energy dissipation capacity. Various researchers have investigated different bracing configurations, including concentric, eccentric, buckling restrained, and X-bracing systems. Most studies reported that braced structures exhibit better seismic resistance compared to unbraced frames. The review also highlights the importance of structural configuration and lateral load-resisting systems in controlling storey drift, displacement, and overall structural stability.

- Most studies focus on a single bracing type rather than comparing different structural configurations.
- Limited research is available on steel braced frames with different plan shapes such as Square, L, C, and T configurations.
- The influence of bracing location at corners, faces, and core regions has not been extensively investigated.

Objectives

1. To study the lateral load-resisting systems and load distribution in high-rise steel buildings.
2. To investigate the behavior of high-rise steel structures with X bracing systems under seismic loading conditions as per the revised Indian Standard IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016.

METHODOLOGY

1. Data Collection:

- Collection of literature related to steel braced frames, seismic analysis, and lateral load-resisting systems.
- Selection of design parameters based on relevant Indian Standard codes and steel building requirements.

2. Modeling:

- Modeling of steel framed buildings with different plan configurations in ETABS.
- Four plan shapes considered:
 - Model 1: Square Shape
 - Model 2: L Shape
 - Model 3: C Shape
 - Model 4: T Shape
- Steel X-bracing provided at different locations:
 - Corner Bracing
 - Face Bracing
 - Core Bracing

3. Loading Conditions:

- Dead Load (DL)
- Live Load (LL) as per IS 875 (Part 2)
- Seismic Load as per IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016
- Load combinations as per IS 800:2007 and IS 1893:2016.

4. Analysis:

- Equivalent Static Analysis.
- Response Spectrum Analysis.

Table 3. Structural Configuration

Number of Stories	G+30
Height of Each Stories	3 m
Height at 15th, 20th and 25th	3.2 m
Dimension of building	30m X 30m building size
Size of Beam	B 300 x 650
Size Of Columnn	C 300 x 750
Slab Thickness	S150 mm

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Modeling in Etabs.

The study's design considerations for the building structure, which includes varying parameters of structure such as changes in location of X brace and geometric configuration. Initially planned for a building for G+30 with RCC building in a seismic Zone III with the same area.

Fig 1 Square Shape

Fig 2 L Shape

Fig 3 C Shape

Fig 4 T Shape

2) Results For Model Having Bracing At Corner

Table 1 Lateral Displacement mm - SB at Corner

Lateral Displacement mm - SB at Corner				
Direction	Square Shape	L Shape	C Shape	T Shape
X	65.25	83.66	41.34	76.05
Y	116.09	120.88	130.15	128.09

The lateral displacement values varied significantly with plan configuration under seismic loading. Lower displacement indicates higher stiffness and better lateral load resistance.

- In X-direction, C-shape showed the minimum displacement of 41.34 mm, which is 36.64% lower than Square shape.
- L-shape showed the maximum displacement of 83.66 mm in X-direction, which is 28.21% higher than Square shape.
- In Y-direction, Square shape showed the minimum displacement of 116.09 mm.
- C-shape and T-shape showed 12.11% and 10.34% higher displacement respectively compared to Square shape in Y-direction.
- Lower lateral displacement indicates better structural stiffness and seismic stability

Corner bracing significantly reduced displacement in the X-direction for the C-shape building, while the Square shape performed better in the Y-direction due to its symmetric configuration

3) Results For Model Having Bracing At Face

Table 2 Lateral Displacement mm - SB at Face

Lateral Displacement mm - SB at Face				
Direction	Square Shape	L Shape	C Shape	T Shape
X	60.67	84.18	43.97	112.9
Y	100.68	125.07	119.92	118.7

The lateral displacement values varied with the plan configuration under face bracing conditions. Lower displacement indicates better stiffness and improved resistance against lateral loads.

- In X-direction, C-shape showed the minimum displacement of 43.97 mm, which is 27.53% lower than Square shape.
- T-shape showed the maximum displacement of 112.9 mm in X-direction, which is 86.08% higher than Square shape.
- In Y-direction, Square shape recorded the minimum displacement of 100.68 mm.
- L-shape, C-shape, and T-shape showed 24.22%, 19.11%, and 17.90% higher displacement respectively compared to Square shape in Y-direction.
- Lower lateral displacement indicates higher structural stiffness and better seismic performance.

Face bracing significantly improved the lateral stability of the C-shape building in X-direction, while the Square shape performed better in Y-direction due to its regular and symmetric configuration.

4) Results For Model Having Bracing At Core

Table 3 Lateral Displacement mm - SB at Core

Lateral Displacement mm - SW at Core				
Direction	Square Shape	L Shape	C Shape	T Shape
X	59.87	82.82	43.49	94.21
Y	98.26	132.42	119.22	97.82

The lateral displacement values for core bracing varied with different plan configurations under seismic loading. Lower displacement indicates better stiffness and improved lateral load resistance.

- In X-direction, C-shape showed the minimum displacement of 43.49 mm, which is 27.36% lower than Square shape.
- L-shape showed the maximum displacement of 82.82 mm in X-direction, which is 38.33% higher than Square shape.
- In Y-direction, T-shape showed the minimum displacement of 97.82 mm, which is 0.45% lower than Square shape.

- L-shape and C-shape showed 34.76% and 21.33% higher displacement respectively compared to Square shape in Y-direction.
- Lower lateral displacement indicates greater stiffness and better seismic stability.

Core bracing significantly improved the lateral performance of the C-shape building in X-direction, while the T-shape building performed better in Y-direction due to improved stiffness and load distribution.

Table 4 Overall Comparative Performance

Bracing Location	Best Shape	Reason
Corner Bracing	T Shape	Lower time period and higher frequency
Face Bracing	Square Shape / C Shape	Better stability and lower displacement
Core Bracing	T Shape	Improved stiffness and seismic behavior
Overall Best for X-direction Stability	C Shape	Minimum lateral displacement
Overall Best for Y-direction Stability	Square Shape / T Shape	Lower displacement values
Overall Best Seismic Performance	T Shape	Higher stiffness and improved dynamic response

CONCLUSION

- Steel bracing significantly improved the seismic performance of all building models by increasing stiffness and reducing lateral displacement.
- The structural response was strongly influenced by both the building plan configuration and the bracing location.
- The C-shape building showed the minimum lateral displacement in the X-direction for most bracing arrangements.
- The Square shape building exhibited better stability in the Y-direction due to its symmetrical configuration.
- The T-shape building demonstrated lower time period and higher natural frequency, indicating better dynamic performance.
- Core bracing provided the most effective improvement in overall structural behavior compared to corner and face bracing.
- Corner and face bracing also enhanced seismic resistance but were comparatively less effective than core bracing.
- The T-shape building with core bracing showed the best overall seismic performance among all studied models.
- Proper selection of bracing location and building configuration can effectively reduce seismic response and improve structural safety.
- Core bracing in T-shaped steel buildings is recommended for achieving better stiffness, stability, and earthquake resistance.

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